

The Degree Of Secondary School Principals` Commitment To The Quality Standards Of Governance From Their Teachers` Perspectiver

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 12,2025</p> <p>Accepted: February 23,2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Governance QualityStandards, Schools,Secondary School Principals.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18761026</p>	<p><i>The present study aims at revealing the degree of secondary school principals` commitment in Ma'an Governorate to the quality standards of governance from their teachers` perspectives. The sample contains (1317) teachers of both genders in the Directorates of Education of Ma'an Governorate. They were chosen by a cluster random method. To achieve the study purposes; an evaluation tool has been developed which finally consists of (39) items. Its validity and stability have been verified. The results of this study indicate that the estimates of the degree of secondary school principals` commitment in Ma'an Governorate to the quality standards of governance from their teachers` perspectives ranged within the moderate level. The standard of institutional integrity has ranked first, followed by the standard of management and leadership, then the standard of learning and teaching. Moreover, there aren't any statistically significant differences ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) attributed to the years of experience variable in all domains. On the other hand, there are statistically significant differences ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) attributed to the qualification variable in the institutional integrity domain, in favor of the bachelor holders. In addition, there are statistically significant differences ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) attributed to the gender variable in the learning outcomes domain, in favor of females. The study recommends the necessity of activating quality standards of governance in public schools by urging school principals to adhere to these standards.</i></p>

Introduction

The world witnesses rapid developments in all fields, especially the education one, so we always find the educational institutions in a case of imbalance. This imposes the necessity of overcoming a lot of challenges; to keep pace with these rapid developments by searching on modern and effective methods to dispense with the traditional ones in administrative and regulatory operations for all organizational levels.

Education institutions suffer from many problems and challenges, including the lack of effectiveness of their departments, weak autonomy, the complexity of regulations and instructions, their ambiguity and contradiction, the multiplicity of levels or administrative circles, the hierarchy in writing reports, controlling and making decisions, neglecting the role of middle and executive administrative leaders, as well as the administrative structures. The organizational regulation and instructions are also described with slow procedures, centralization in decision-making, the prevalence of the administrative bureaucratic phenomenon represented by acute centralization, the uniqueness of senior management in decision-making, the weak participation of faculty, administrative and student members in the decision-making process, resistance to change and development, and lack of excellence and creativity (Al- Erainy, 2016).

Today, governance is one of the most important modern topics to the administrative field in general and educational in particular. This topic is considered a new future direction for its approval as a right positive methodology, which supports the educational institutions through a scientific and practical accumulation, which increasingly invites to activate governance requirements, and make it one of the governmental work priorities and general administrative systems and educational institutions activities; to achieve its objects with maximum effectiveness away from all weakness cases in managing its affairs (Al-Shunak, 2009).

Governance ensures the operations which manages the business of institution in a wise way which bases on disciplined rules and standards, which briefly represents on sharing all parties in institution in making decisions process, and clearly providing information for all related parties and citizens, to avoid the administration corruption cases, for reaching the highest degree of efficiency in the work and productivity (Hatamela & Salama, 2017).

Governance is one of most important evaluation guides which takes over on interests of all academic and non-academic institutions. It characterizes as a new administrative structure which bases on clarity and integrity. It also characterizes as efficient resources usage by building regulations and standards matrixes which adjusts the work, improves its outputs by the way that achieves the institution aim to be able in achieving the

quality and competition. Spreading governance culture is basically achieving best judgment with its different administrative rules. This will lead it to a state, practical, trend and health system which works on strengthening institutions and ensuring the safety of their tendencies and integrity of their ethics (Abu-Daka, 2013).

Governance application is a mean to avoid the negative surprises. It regulates the relationship in any system by identifying the achievement time through clarity and credibility in making decision. It is a group of rules, regulations and decisions which aim to achieve the quality and distinction in performance through choosing suitable methods. Governance attempts to achieve the institution aims and plans because it is based on fairness and justice to strengthen the law, as a comprehensive system which includes measuring a new administration performance. It is considered as an indicator to the existence of supervisory methods, which prevents any negative effect on an institution's activity (Ghadban, 2015).

In the previous years, Jordan has greatly expanded in the education field, through building new and varied educational institutions; to keep pace with the discipline diversity and increasingly demand for education, and welcome to large number of students from abroad. Governorate depends on diversity and quality under this expansion and this considers an important and necessary matter in the existence of local, regional and international challenges which face the education such as competition and great technical development and policies, rules, variable regulations from one side and requirements, market needs and global competition from another side. In addition, it moves towards linking education with development and its plans in all fields, so most of its strategies headed to support the based relationship between education and development through working on the performance quality (Battah, 2017).

Based in the great importance of governance, this study comes to secure the measurement of governance quality by providing psychometric properties of validity and reliability, which fit to measure the use of governance standards by the principals in Jordanian education institutions.

Statement of the Study and Its Questions

In the last years, there is a great interest on the topic of governance in education, as conferences were held that one of the most important recommendations is the acceleration of applying the principles of governance in education institutions. United Nations Organization for education, learn and culture recommended the need to apply governance principals in the learning domain (Nasser Al-din, 2012). A lot of studies were conducted which recommend to conduct scientific researches on the degree of applying governance in the education institutions such as Al-Zabn (2017) and Al-Kasr (2018).

In addition, it is necessary to know the reality of learning institutions, by viewing the sources of weaknesses; to treat and manipulate them successfully, and viewing the sources of strengths to better exploit them, ensure their quality and develop their roles, for continuing, competition and facing challenges to provide a trained human models and qualified for the country, which are important in enhancing the projects and the great increasing on demanding education. The national strategy for developing human resources in Jordan includes the governance in education topic, and it is considered as an essential component of its developing components (Yirdaw, 2016).

The interest in governance increased after the failures and stumbling blocks faced by many organizations, which increased the need for governance that includes mechanisms that ensure efficient decision-making and improve the organization's performance. Good functioning, stability and quality improvement in different organizations, governance does not refer much to what institutions do, but rather to how they perform their work, i.e. the methods and means through which the institution defines its duties and organizes itself to achieve the purpose of its existence. Governance can be understood as the distribution of authority and tasks among the units within a larger entity, the methods of communication and control among them, and the functioning of the relationships between the entity and the surrounding environment (Marzouk, 2012).

The statement of the study specifically lies on investigating the following questions:

- 1- What is the degree of secondary school principals' commitment in Ma'an Governorate to the quality standards of governance from their teachers' perspectives?
- 2- Are there any statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) in the degree of secondary school principals' commitment in Ma'an Governorate to the quality standards of governance from their teachers' perspectives, which is due to (gender, qualification and experience)?

Study Purposes

- 1- Identifying on the degree of secondary school principals' commitment in Ma'an Governorate to the quality standards of governance from their teachers' perspectives.

- 2- Identifying if there are statistically significant differences on the degree of secondary school principals' commitment in Ma'an Governorate to the quality standards of governance from their teachers' perspectives which is due to (gender, qualification and experience).

The Significance of the Study

- This study gains its importance from the importance of the topic it deals with, which is to reveal the degree of commitment of secondary school principals in Ma'an Governorate to the standards of governance quality from the point of view of their teachers.
- Providing important information to the Ministry of Education in the Kingdom on the degree of commitment of Jordanian government secondary school principals to the quality standards of governance.
- It is expected that this study will help officials in the Ministry of Education to set standards for the profession of school administration in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.
- The public high school principals can identify the opinions of those who work and deal with. This may motivate them to make the amendment or change in their behavior with the parties to the educational process on the one hand, and to perform their tasks in a better way towards achieving the desired goals On the other hand.

Conceptual and Procedural Concepts:

- Governance is "a group of mechanisms, procedures, laws, regulations and decisions which ensure discipline, limpidity and justice, so it leads to achieve quality and excellence in its role through the administration role to use available resources and through which achieving the best possible benefit for all parties and community in general" (Ali & Shhada, 2007- 42).
- Governance in education institution is "the education institution ability to achieve its purposes with a high level, improving its role by following effective plans and suitable methods through smart administration", Al- Erainy, 2016- 126).
- Governance is "Practices that ensure optimal use of the administrative powers through which it can be Achieving the organization's objectives, and applying the best practices and documented methodologies that are being worked with Maintaining the rights and satisfaction of customers and decision-makers", (Bahrain Governance Guide, 2013- 17).
- Quality is: "Uniting efforts and investing the various capacities of the management and workers collectively to improve the management approach and its specifications ", (Alimat, 2004- 16)

Study Limits:

The study was limited to the following limits: -

Temporal limits: The study was conducted in the first of the academic year 2020-2021.

- Human limits: the study was limited to teachers of government secondary schools in Ma'an Governorate.

Spatial limits: The study included the directorates of education in Ma'an Governorate (Ma'an Kasbah, Petra, Shobak, and the Southern Badia).

Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies:

Governance Concept

The concepts of governance vary according to how they are viewed and the purpose of their use, but they all agree in the ability of governance to support transparency, reform negative practices in institutions in general, as well as monitoring to eliminate corruption resulting from weak accountability, more transparency. It aims at increasing credibility, accountability and democracy through presence of a developed financial and administrative system, the activation of decentralization and reforming personnel affairs (Azab, 2008).

Nasser Al-din (2012, 347) states that: "A system to address the administrative tyranny that arises through the hierarchical relationship between principals and employees within organizations".

Al-Kasr (2018, 392) defines it as: "Controlling institutions within a general framework that brings together global systems and standards, which are a set of laws, regulations and decisions that aim to achieve

quality and excellence in performance by choosing appropriate and effective methods to achieve the plans and goals of the organization."

Accordingly, it can be said that governance is a practical methodology which aims at raising the efficiency of the institution by applying the principles of transparency, accountability and participation; in order to obtain the highest quality and the lowest cost.

As for governance in education and its institutions, its definitions have also varied. Education governance has been defined by Ahmed & Zaki (2017, 68) as "The system by which educational institutions are managed, directed, and monitored; to achieve quality and excellence in their performance within the framework of a set of laws, procedures and standards that are defined by them. It defines the ethics of professional practice, including the achievement of integrity, transparency, accountability and participation of all parties related to the institutions."

Battah (2017) refers to the concept of governance as a rational management method that enables the achievement of the goals set through participation, accountability and transparency. According to this definition, the basic pillars of the concept of governance can be stated as follows:

- Governance is an administrative or administrative philosophy method.
- Governance is a mean for reaching to desired purposes whether it is public or private.
- Governance principal pillars is (participating, questioning and transparency).

Governance Importance

The importance of governance represents in providing a regulatory structure for educational institution which identify by its role the responsibility lines, through which the educational institutions achieve their purposes. In addition to of what it represents as an observation tool, we can identify its importance in education institutions management as follows: (Al- Erainy (2016), Muhsen(2009) and Battah (2017)

- 1- Contributing to create independent institutions with their governing councils and bodies, whose responsibilities are to define the strategic direction for these institutions, and to ensure the effectiveness, quality and efficiency of their management.
- 2- achieving purposes with the best possibly methods.
- 3- Identifying weaknesses and failure in performance, outputs and services.
- 4- Ensuring balance between long-term strategic responsibilities and short-term operation responsibilities.
- 5- Including interests and rights of staff without discrimination.
- 6- Governance is an observation system and self-supervision, which leads to legal application safety of the legislation.

Governance Purposes:

Battah & Al-Taani (2016) state that the principal governance purposes as follows:

- Developing suitable structure which achieves the purposes of organization.
- Improving the efficiency of organization.
- Observing and following up the performance.
- Revising and amending laws which regulate the work in organization.
- Reforming the high administration, strengthening questioning and rising the trust degree.
- Enabling both organizations and institutions from getting on transforming local supporters and foreigners.
- Achieving an economic efficiency at both full and partial levels.

Governance Models:

Trakman(2008) identifies to four governance models as follows:

- 1- Academic Model: this form is the most cohesive with traditions, as university subjects to the governance of academic officers in this form. In addition, to the academic officers have the strongest opinion and more wider representation in identifying the message and managing of university, there are a lot of methods to build as this curriculum by giving powers to take decisions for the academic association, via having an effective acting of the academic officers in governance boards, or through nominating one of eminent academics as a head or superior in institution.
- 2- Company Model: Corporate governance has emerged as a response to the financial crises, as well as the need to manage its financial resources in a more responsible manner. The corporate governance works under the application of corporate methods such as the financial issue. academy. This model usually refers to that the head of university is characterized by an administrative occupation similar to

managing occupation of companies, not only academic occupation of the academic institutions management.

- 3- Trustees Model: governance through trustees gives an administration the trustees authorities. This usually comes as board of trustees which has not elected members in institution, who don't represent the varied interests' owners. In fact, the board of trustees has more responsibilities including those related to the trust duty and the due purpose; to protect guardianship, including the announcement about any factors which form conflict with interests and guardians.
- 4- Interests' Owners Model: this model happens when governance based on great number of interests' owners, including students, academic officers, graduates, supported companies and local society.

Quality Concept:

Quality in Arabic language, as in Al-waseet lexicon, refers to its tripartite verb (Jad). Its origin is (Jaouda) which means that things get better. It is also said: he does his work well (*IbnManzour*, 2004).

The conceptual definition of quality appears in the International Organization for Standardization which defines it as: "a group of descriptions and properties that a good or service is characterized which leads to possibility of achieving announced or hidden desires" (Ahmed & Zaki, 2017- 67).

Azab (2008- 64) defines it as: "Any institution or particular organization which can submit service with high quality and perfection; to fulfill the needs and desires of people in a way that agrees with their expectations about this service. This can reach to their satisfaction and pleasure."

s Attia (2008- 37) defines it as the completion of features and properties of a product or service; to serve identified and known needs and demands for beneficiaries.

Depending on the previous definitions, the researcher defines quality as follows: the specificity, good performance and perfection as a total for the product properties and features whether it's material or humanly, or continuous service which presents by institution; to satisfy beneficiaries the announced and hidden needs, and fulfill their desires, ambitions and expectations with high efficiency and satisfaction.

Quality in Education

If the case of adjust quality is important in economical institution, it is the most important in educational institutions and systems caused by the increased cost of education alongside the international inflation rates, poor quality of some educational outputs and poor correlation with labor market. As a result, it negatively effects on developing rates, the ability of society on achieving its ambitions and purposes. The adjusting of education quality is a method to assure that the educational process and administration, training workers and managers and educational developing in educational institutions; all of them happen according to a certified planes and standard specification (Al-Badi, 2010).

Quality Purposes

The applying of the quality assurance system in educational institutions aims at fulfilling a lot of purposes. Some of them reflect interests and demands of countries' government, while others reflect the interior needs for education institution. Ata (2013) characterized the purposes of the quality assurance system in educational institutions into three types as follows:

- 1- Quality observation: it is one of the most important purposes and roles for the countries' governments to achieve the outputs of education system to the minimum quality demands, and with the private educational institution and continuation of its speeding and expansion. The need of government has increased to serious and cautious follow up to the quality level to these institutions; to ensure the educational outputs relevance with the need of labor-market, and provide educational institutional services to the purposes of national developing.

- 2- Questioning and Transparency: the applying of the quality assurance system aims at forcing responsibility on conformity of objective standards and confirming that everyone takes responsibility to achieve quality in processes, who is responsible for it, as everyone shall do his tasks alongside training programs and procedures which were identified by the quality assurance system.

3- Improving the present activities: the applying of the quality assurance system helps to improve the present activities in educational institutions, through the important procedure which is self-evaluation; to supply the feedback for decision's makers about the unit which is evaluated, showing the weakness and strengthens points. This helps them in putting strategies, plans and making procedures capable of filling gaps, correct wrongs and making optimal use from possibilities to achieve better roles.

The success of applying the quality in educational institutions depends on availability of group of terms which were explained by Salama (2015) as follows:

- 1- The presence of a climate of trust between those who conduct these operations and those involved.
- 2- Doing this through workflow and not its end.
- 3- Providing information can be used to guide an individual towards subsequent steps to be followed in direct conduct for the continued improvement.
- 4- It does not include decisions of an administrative nature. It is content with describing the reality with its strengths and weaknesses.

Available capabilities and potential risks: It is recommended that these processes take place periodically and regularly.

The Relationship between Quality and Governance:

Good governance guides decision making. It is characterized by rationality, disclosure and transparency leading to the achievement of efficiency and effectiveness at the organizational level. Institutional governance is a vital element that will allow those in charge of those institutions to design, implement, monitor and evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of performance. Quality works towards adopting standards of governance and laying down its rules; in order to increase the capacity of institutions to excel, and to face current and future challenges. (Ghader, 2012).

Previous Studies:

Sharaf (2015) A study aimed at identifying the reality of implementing governance systems, and the obstacles in Palestinian universities from the point of view of faculty deans and heads of academic departments in the West Bank, and its impact on the variables of gender, job title, years of experience and the university by using the descriptive approach. The study was applied on a sample of (105) of deans and heads of departments. The study indicated that there is a large degree on the reality of implementing governance in Palestinian universities from the point of view of faculty deans and academic department heads in the West Bank. It is attributed to the study variables, and the existence of differences according to the university variable in favor of Birzeit University.

Fabrice&Mitterle(2015)A study aimed at discovering the relationship between governance and quality assurance and the importance of guidance at the state level to help education achieve its mission effectively. It presents the reasons that have made governance and quality a critical issue for education. The researchers used the descriptive approach by studying the main governance models in universities over a period of ten years. He studied quality assurance guides, and a set of principles developed by ministries, institutional authorities, quality assurance agencies, and conferences of university presidents, and he discusses the distinction between governance arrangements and quality guidelines, as well as the possible need to define appropriate guidance for educational institutions in all aspects of education. At the same time, quality assurance has risen around the world aiming to address the balance between the autonomy granted to institutions and accountability.

Mahmoud's (2016) study aimed at identifying the degree of application of the principles of governance and its relationship to the quality of work procedures in the directorates of education in the northern governorates of the West Bank from the viewpoints of government secondary school principals. It was applied on a random stratified sample of (173) principals and principals. The correlation approach and the questionnaire were used to collect data. The results of the study showed that the degree of application of the principles of governance was moderate. Moreover, there is a statistically significant positive correlation between the degree of application of the principles of governance and the degree of quality of work procedures in the education directorates in the governorates of the northern West Bank from the viewpoints of government secondary school principals.

Yirdaw(2016)conducted a study which aimed at identifying the role of leadership and governance factors in private education institutions in Ethiopia that may contribute to improving the quality of education, and by using the qualitative case study methodology. Interviews were conducted with administrative officials in six

private educational institutions in Ethiopia. Their views were compared with other information available to the public. The results indicate that these institutions face an ongoing challenge to balance government requirements and stakeholder demands in an environment where funding is offered, qualified trainers are scarce, infrastructure is weak, qualified weak students, and the regulatory environment is biased. In addition, the study revealed that most education leaders believe that addressing management more effectively can significantly improve the quality of education, and include recommendations of policy makers, regulatory agencies, and education institution leaders ensuring the availability and proper use of qualified trainers, adequate infrastructure, and the importance of education governance; to ensure its quality.

Al-Zabn(2017) conducted a study which aimed to explore the degree to which administrators and academics practice educational governance in Jordanian universities and its relationship to the delegation of authority from the point of view of faculty members. To achieve this goal, the researcher selected a sample of the study consisting of (261) faculty members who were chosen by the random stratified method. The results of the study showed that the degree of academic directors` practice of educational governance in Jordanian universities from the viewpoint of the faculty members was moderate, and that the degree of their delegation of authority was moderate as well.

Al-Bustanji(2018) conducted a study aimed at investigating the relationship between the degree of academic leaders` practice of governance in Jordanian universities in the capital, Amman, and its relationship to the degree of availability of (Six Sigma) standards from the point of view of faculty members. The descriptive approach was used to achieve this goal. A sample of the study consisting of (440) members was chosen. The teaching was chosen by the random stratified method. Two tools were developed to collect data. The results of the study showed that the degree of academic leaders` practice of governance in Jordanian universities from the faculty members` point of view was medium, and that the degree of availability of (Six Sigma) standards was moderate. There is existence of a positive statistically significant relationship between the variables of the degree of governance practice and the degree of availability of (Six Sigma) standards. There are no statistically significant differences in the means of the response of faculty members to the degree of academic leaders` practice of governance due to variables of gender, supervisory authority, academic rank and years of experience. There are statistically significant differences in the means of response of faculty members to the degree of governance practice of the college variable in favor of humanitarian colleges.

Al-Kasr(2018) conducted a study which aimed to identify the definition of universities governance, and how to the extent of its implementation of developing universities role, identifying on the relationship on implementation of comprehensive quality standards through activating administrative governance. To achieve these purposes, the descriptive method was used distributing the study tool on the sample which including staff and academic leaders in private universities in Riyadh. The study revealed that the reality is high in governance application in private universities in Riyadh as it reached (4016). In addition, there is a relationship between the application of institutional quality standards and activate the administrative governance in private universities in Riyadh. The study ended with some recommendations such as: it must be used regulations and related legislation with standards and principals of universities governance and setting independent committees inside private universities, to follow up fulfillment standards and evaluation of governance, working on spreading good governance culture which includes transparency, questioning and participating standards.

Abdeldjabar(2019) conducted a study aimed to reveal the experience of the United Kingdom in the governance of educational institutions; in order to ensure the quality of its outputs, and to analyze its experience in the governance of its universities with the aim of quality assurance by studying their application of governance mechanisms. The researcher used the analytical qualitative approach for educational institutions in the United Kingdom. The results showed that the indicators (student admission The independence of management, diversification of funding sources such as partnership and marketing of university services as well as the role of private financing, relying on transparency, participation, accountability and the role of review in the proper utilization of its resources) have contributed to achieving the quality of education in the United Kingdom, as it has accumulated over the years. Its objectives are among the advantages of both the public and private sectors, as it benefits from the public sector by directing its services to satisfy the general needs of society. It also derives from the private sector strategies for obtaining financial resources such as relying on the marketing approach in order to achieve profits to be re-spent on education, scientific research and access to quality And continuous development.

Comments on the Previous Studies

From the above, the previous studies could vary which talked about governance, and focus on the governance importance in educational institutions administration. The studies confirmed the necessity on

heading to apply governance standards as the studies of Al-Bustanjis(2018), Al-Kasr (2018), Al-Zabn(2017) and Fabrice&Mitterle(2015).

The studies could vary when the followed methodology to achieve results, as it depended on analytical descriptive method Sharaf's study (2015), and correlation method as Mahmoud's study (2016), by using questionnaire and studying state Yirdaw's study (2016).

The researcher benefited from the previous studies in scientific methodology that these studies followed. Also he benefited from in the way of view matter and design studying tool, which showed the need to exist the standardized measure to apply governance standards and how the extent of its quality.

The current study differed from the previous one in terms of spatial and temporal limits and the sample, variable and tool of study. The current study differed from the related subject of previous one in terms of its research in developing governance quality measure in Jordanian educational institution.

Study Method:

Descriptive sampling method was used; to achieve the purposes of this study and answer its questions.

Study Society:

The study society is all male and female teachers of governmental secondary schools in Education Directorates in Ma'an Governorate through the first semester of academic year (2020- 2021), that their number reached (1317) from both male and female teachers according to Education sources in academic year of (2020-2021), who are distributed on directorates (Education KasbhMa'an, Petra, Shobak, the North Bank).

Study Sample:

The sample of study composed to (168) of both male and female teachers, who formed about (12%) of the original society size for study. They were chosen by randomly. Table (1) explains a description of study sample according to its independent variables.

Table (1)
The Distributing on Study Sample According to Variables of Gender, Scientific Qualification and Experience

Variable	Variable Classes	Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	72	43%
	Female	96	57%
Qualification	Bachelor	109	65%
	Postgraduate Studies	59	35%
Experience	Below 5 years	54	32%
	From 5 to 10 years	71	42%
	Over 10 years	43	26%
Total		168	100%

Study Tool: The study tool consisted of a questionnaire that was developed based on previous studies, and governance indicators in the schools of the Jordanian Ministry of Education, to suit the purpose of the study. Hand the answer for each paragraph, out of five responses (according to the five-point Likert scale). This tool, in its first form, contains three domains (learning and education, leadership and managing, institutional and integrity) in about (45) items, answers in each item were composed to five responses (according to Fifth Likart Scale).

Tool Validity: The validity of the tool was verified using apparent validity by presenting it to (10) judges specialized in the subject of study in curricula and teaching methods, measurement and evaluation and quality assurance; in order to express an opinion on each of the paragraphs that were placed in the tool and in each area to which the paragraph belongs and the drafting of each paragraph in terms of the language and the field to which it belongs, as the paragraph agreed upon by (80%) of the judges was retained. The opinions were summarized as follows: Merging some paragraphs due to their interconnectedness, the difficulty of separating them, canceling the repeated paragraphs and deleting the paragraphs that are not related to the topic, so that the

number of paragraphs of the tool in its final form becomes 39 paragraphs and is divided into three areas (learning and education, leadership and management, Integrity and institutional).

Tool Reliability: Tool Reliability was verified with Internal Consistency method of the questionnaire by using Cronbach Alpha method. The calculated reliability coefficient is (0.86). Table (2) shows Cronbach Alpha of reliability coefficient for domains which ranges between (0.75- 0.88).

Table (2)
Calculated Reliability Coefficient of Studying Tool

Domain	Cronbach Alpha Reliability
Learning and Teaching	0.86
Leadership and Managing	0.84
Institutional and Integrity	0.88
Total	0.86

Table (2) shows the values of reliability factors which are accepted and the measurement is usable.

Study Variables:

- 1- Independent variables: genders which have two levels: 1.male 2.female
- 2- Scientific qualification which has two levels: 1.Bachelor 2.postgraduate studies
- 3- Work experience years which have three levels: 1.below 5years 2.from 5 to 10 3.over 10 years

Results and their Discussion

First: results related to the basic question which is its text: what is the degree of commitment secondary schools managers in Ma'an governorate with governance quality standards from their teachers' perspectives? To answer this question: means, standard deviation, percentage and the total degree of questionnaire were used for each item and domain. It is arranged in descending order according to mean scores, as the appendage no. (4) showed the descending items arrangements for each domain according to mean scores, standard deviations, percentages and commitment degree of the items tool and its domains. And this is shown in Table (3):

Table (3)

Rank	Number	Standard	Mean Scores	Standard Deviations	Evaluating Degree
1	4	The manager focuses on merge the knowledge with life.	3.70	0.72	High
2	11	The manager focuses on building values and positive trends among students.	3.61	0.79	Moderate
3	8	The manager follows up the diversity in teaching strategies and taking into account the individual differences.	3.52	0.81	Moderate
4	3	The manager employs skills of dealing with disabilities students	3.50	0.83	Moderate
5	1	The manager follows students' academic achievements with transparency and equity.	3.47	0.85	Moderate
6	2	The manager uses the individual and accumulated results of students to support the school development plan.	3.40	0.86	Moderate
7	9	The manager provides healthy and safety environment.	3.36	0.87	Moderate
8	13	The manager does maintenance in good and continuous way.	3.33	0.89	Moderate
9	7	The manager is careful to represent the workers in school as an ideal example for	3.30	0.91	Moderate

		students.			
10	12	The manager provides a diversity education.	3.26	0.94	Moderate
11	6	The manager provides diversity opportunities for students to participate in individual activities.	3.26	0.97	Moderate
12	10	The manager issues interior standards to regulate the conduct of both students and workers.	3.12	0.81	Moderate
13	5	The manager identifies the work strategies depending on accurate objective studies.	3.10	0.48	Moderate
The domain as a whole			3.38	0.76	Moderate

Mean scores and Standard Deviations for Estimates of Study's Sample Members on Tool Domains in Descending Order

Rank	Number	Quality insurance standards	Mean Scores	Standard deviation	Available degree
1	3	Institutionalization integrity	3.55	0.87	Moderate
2	1	Leadership and managing	3.53	0.71	Moderate
3	5	Learning and teaching	3.38	0.76	Moderate
Tool as a whole			3.49	0.77	Moderate

Table (3) shows that the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate came at a moderate level from the point of view of their teachers, as the mean score of the study sample individuals' estimates on the tool domains has reached (3.49) with a standard deviation (0.77), whereas the standard of integrity and institutionalization came in the first rank with a mean score (3.55) with a moderate level, and a standard deviation (0.87), while learning and teaching ranked last, with a mean score (3.38) with a moderate level, and a standard deviation of (0.76).

Mean scores and standard deviations have been calculated for the commitment degree domains of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards from the point of views of their teachers as follows:

The First Domain: Learning and Teaching:

Mean scores and standard deviations have been calculated for the commitment degree domains of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards from the point of views of their teachers in items of this standard which came as shown in Table (5):

Table (5)

Mean scores and Standard Deviations for the Estimates of Teaching Sample Members on Learning and Teaching Which Were Arranged in Descending Order

Table (5) shows that all items in content domain came in a moderate level except an item came in a high level, the item (4) which states: "the manager focuses on merge the knowledge with life" came in the first rank with a mean score (3.70), and a standard deviation (0.72), while the item (23) which states: "the manager identifies the work strategies depending on accurate objective studies" in the last rank with a moderate level with a mean score which reached (3.10), and a standard deviation (0.48).

The Second Domain: Managing and Leadership:

Mean scores and standard deviations have been calculated for the commitment degree domains of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards from the point of views of their teachers in items of this standard which came as shown in Table (6):

Table (6)

Mean scores and Standard Deviations for the Estimates of Teaching Sample Members on Managing and Leadership Standards Which Were Arranged in Descending Order

Rank	Number	Standard	Mean Scores	Standard Deviations	Evaluating Degree
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1	16	The manager is careful to hold sessions for officers to achieve their skills to be fit their roles.	4.12	0.72	High
2	22	The manager puts school plans by participating with all related parties.	3.92	0.79	High
3	19	The manager provides chances for achieving workers professionally.	3.65	0.85	Moderate
4	14	The manager does an alternative partnership with local society to support the school development.	3.63	0.86	Moderate
5	18	The manager evaluates all workers' performance in institutions periodically and regularly.	3.53	0.91	Moderate
6	15	The manager revises and develops all procedures to evaluate the role regularly.	3.46	0.94	Moderate
6	23	The manager provides chances of participatory leadership for workers in school.	3.46	0.97	Moderate
8	25	The manager invests material and human resources in school.	3.44	0.18	Moderate
9	20	The manager encourages distinguished workers in their performance.	3.39	0.23	Moderate
10	17	The manager uses the questioning to improve officers' performance.	3.33	0.88	Moderate
11	21	The manager authorizes some powers for workers to enable them easily to do their works.	3.28	0.65	Moderate
12	24	The manager provides a clear model of the completed works (decisions- results).	3.20	0.72	Moderate
The domain as a whole			3.53	0.71	Moderate

Table (6) shows that all items in activities and means domain came in a moderate level, except four items came in a high level, the item (16) which states: "the manager is careful to held sessions for officers to achieve their skills to be fit their roles." came in the first rank with a mean score which reached (4.12), and a standard deviation (0.72), while the item (24) which states: "the manager provides a clear model of the completed works (decisions- results)." in the last rank with a moderate level with a mean score which reached (3.20), and a standard deviation (0.72).

The Third Domain: Institutionalization and Integrity

Mean scores and standard deviations have been calculated for the commitment degree domains of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards from the point of views of their teachers in items of this standard which came as shown in Table (7):

Table (7)

Mean scores and Standard Deviations for the Estimates of Teaching Sample Members on Institutionalization and Integrity standards Which Were Aranged in Descending Order

Rank	Number	Standard	Mean scores	Standard Deviations	Evaluating Degree
1	30	The applied (rules and regulations) in school is characterized by clarity.	3.74	0.71	High
2	35	Transparency policy is authenticated in school and periodically publishes and evaluates it clearly and completely.	3.70	0.86	Moderate
3	29	Procedures are provided in school to achieve equity and equal opportunities.	3.69	0.83	Moderate
4	31	Penalties are applied honestly on all breaches in school.	3.67	0.85	Moderate
5	26	Transparency procedures and principals to grant allowance in school.	3.46	0.89	Moderate
6	37	The institution applies transparency in	3.60	0.94	Moderate

		issuing penalties.			
7	34	The approved principals, allowances and disciplinary penalties are authenticated completely and clearly in grievance cases in school.	3.55	0.96	Moderate
8	32	Grievances processes are applied transparency according to the approved legislations.	3.52	0.77	Moderate
9	39	The school clearly identifies the financing policy for all workers.	3.50	0.62	Moderate
10	28	The school periodically revises and develops the applied principals and procedures.	3.48	0.74	Moderate
11	33	The school provides various mechanisms to receive complaints and suggestions.	3.46	0.79	Moderate
12	27	The school clearly enforces related procedures on workers (appointment, promotion.....)	3.40	0.67	Moderate
13	36	The school is careful for ensuring rights on all levels (students, workers, administrative teachers) and provides suitable atmosphere for them.	3.38	0.83	
14	38	The school gives tasks for officers according to their qualifications.	3.32	0.92	
The domain as a whole			3.55	0.84	Moderate

Table (7) shows that all items in evaluation standards domain came in a moderate level, except anitem came in a high level, the item (30) which states: "the applied (rules and regulations) in school is characterized by clarity." came in the first rank with a mean score which reached (3.74), and a standard deviation (0.71), while the item (38) which states: "the school gives tasks for officers according to their qualifications." in the last rank with a moderate level with a mean score which reached (3.32), and a standard deviation (0.92).

The results refer that the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards from the point of views of their teachers came in a moderate level and, so it needs to a lot of work to increase its efficiency, regarding the quality matter doesn't enable in educational institutions and still in the foundation beginnings. It can inquire that as there aren't any clear standards for governance quality to respect them by secondary schools managers.

In addition, solutions of institutionalization integrity came in the first rank in a moderate level. This result can be indicated as what teachers feel special and not transparency in applying equity and equality inside schools, and often injusticedone on them, lake of estimate of their efforts and what they do.

As for the solutions to the standard of learning and teaching in the last place and at an moderate level. This result can be attributed to the fact that these works are the core of the work of the teachers and they perform them in the nature of the case, which do not fall into the duties of the principal and therefore the teachers, who are the study sample, are not interested in evaluating the principal on its basis.

The Second Question: are there statistically significant differences in ($\alpha=0.05$) in the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards in the points of view of their teachers which due to variables (gender, experience, qualification)? Table (9) shows that:

Table (9)
Mean scores and Standard Deviations for the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an government of governance equality standards on total sign and study variables

Domain		Gender		Qualification		Experience		
		Male	Female	Bachelor	Postgraduate studies	Below 5	From 5 - 10	Over 10
Learning and	Number	72	96	117	51	54	71	43
	Moderate	3.49	3.75	3.53	3.48	3.64	3.53	3.44

Teaching	Deviation	0.595	0.628	0.602	0.609	0.564	0.679	0.543
Leadership and Managing	Number	72	96	117	51	54	71	43
	Moderate	3.27	3.53	3.30	3.26	3.52	3.39	3.29
	Deviation	0.836	0.913	0.746	0.948	0.605	0.697	1.04
Institutionalization and integrity	Number	72	96	117	51	54	71	43
	Moderate	3.49	3.64	3.53	3.50	3.22	3.29	3.36
	Deviation	0.745	0.653	0.721	0.749	0.716	0.849	0.660
Total	Number	72	96	117	51	54	71	43
	Moderate	3.37	3.56	3.42	3.38	3.29	3.35	3.36
	Deviation	0.578	0.690	0.546	0.645	0.856	0.714	0.759

Table (9) shows that there are obvious differences in both mean scores and standard deviations for the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an government of governance equality standards on total sign and study variables, to know if these differences have statistically significant, so multivariate analysis of variance. Table (10) shows that:

Table (10)
Results of multivariate analysis of variance for differences function in the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an government of governance equality standards on total sign and study variables

Differences Source	Domains	Squares Sum	Liberty Degree	Means of Squares	(F) Value	Function Level
Gender	Learning and Education	2.09	1	2.09	5.08	0.240
	Leadership and Management	2.20	1	2.20	3.00	0.084
Hotllings Trace 0.028	Institutionalization integrity	0.753	1	0.753	1.39	*.016
Experience	Learning and Education	0.134	1	1.134	0.374	0.541
	Leadership and Management	0.151	1	0.151	0.206	0.650
Hotllings Trace 0.028	Institutionalization integrity	0.046	1	0.046	0.86	0.770
Experience	Learning and Education	1.94	2	0.972	2.71	0.086
	Leadership and Management	1.42	2	0.712	0.972	0.380
Wilks' Lambda 0.927	Institutionalization integrity	1.5	2	0.769	1.42	0.244
Wrong	Learning and Education	90.916	25	0.358		
	Leadership and Management	185.981	25	0.732		
	Institutionalization integrity	137.594	25	0.542		

*It is statistically significant at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$)

Table (10) shows the following:

- 1- There aren't any statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which due to the variable of experience years in all domains.
- 2- There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), which due to the variable of qualification in institutionalization integrity domain and for the sake of Bachelor after backing mean scores.
- 3- There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) which due to the variable of gender in educational results and after backing to mean scores for the sake of female.

Results show that there aren't any differences in the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards in the points of view of their teachers, which due to the gender variable in leadership and management standard for the sake of female, it can be inquired that as the female are more committed and caring on applying and committed professionally than male, as female always take care to merge with commitment appearance in Educational Directorate.

Also the results show that there are differences in commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards in the points of view of their teachers, which due to the qualification variable in institutionalization integrity for the sake of Bachelor. It can be explained that as the qualified and postgraduate studies owners don't satisfy about the institutionalization integrity of what they feel of iniquity, not upgrading or not benefit with their high qualifications which make them not satisfying on school administration.

The results refer that there aren't any differences in the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards in the points of view of their teachers, which due to an experience variable. This may result from the similarities in the points of view in the commitment degree of secondary schools managers in Ma'an Governorate with governance quality standards.

Recommendations: in the light of the study findings, the recommendation can be as followed:

- 1- The necessity of activating governance quality standards in the governmental schools through encouraging school principals to adhere to these standards.
- 2- Doing awareness and educational sessions of school principals in quality and concepts of governance.
- 3- Doing correlations studies between governance quality standards and other variables in public and private schools.

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